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D.10.3 Report on the implementation and evaluation of communication

Lead Authors: Sorin Hermon, Laura Benassi, Athanasios Koutoupas, Elisabetta Andreassi

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Abstract

The deliverable "Report on the implementation and evaluation of communication" analyses communication and dissemination activities carried out in the E-RIHS PP project and underlines criticalities and possible future implementation.

The analytics tools for the website and social media and the feedback reports for events provide, as a result, an overview of the impact of the communication and dissemination during the E-RIHS PP project.

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Authors (Partner)	CYI			
Responsible Author	Name	Sorin Hermon	Email	s.hermon@cyi.ac.cy
	Partner	CYI	Phone	

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Keywords	Communication, dissemination, smart strategy

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Abbreviations

CMO	Central Management Office
CO	Communication Office
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
HSH	Heritage Science Hub
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PP	Preparatory Phase
RI	Research Infrastructure
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board

Introduction

ERIHS PP is the preparatory phase for establishing a European distributed research infrastructure for Heritage Science. In the last years (2017-2020), many actions, discussions and documents have been finalised, and the E-RIHS community has advanced. It is not easy to communicate a "preparatory phase" project. There are many political and technical issues of any appeal both for the public at large and the researchers. But E-RIHS represents an incredible opportunity for both of them to better know and preserve cultural and natural heritage for the future: this is the main message that people (stakeholders, researchers or a general audience) needs to understand and must make their own.

E-RIHS is listed in RI roadmaps of Italy, France, Greece, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia and Cyprus and is about to be included in the national roadmaps in Belgium, Denmark, Hungary and The Netherlands.

In recent years, the E-RIHS community has enriched its vision and enlarged the networking, creating new paths and meeting new challenges. E-RIHS drafted a consistent scientific strategy, developed an innovation agenda and a training strategy. Now it is ready to go further. In 2019, E-RIHS was recognised as one of the strategic research infrastructures by the Paris Declaration of the Ministries of Culture. In 2020, E-RIHS received the results of the ESFRI monitoring for the 2021 new Roadmap and the evaluation of High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) of the European Commission: E-RIHS is ready for the implementation. Recommendations were suggested, and in the next years, the E-RIHS community will work to improve them.

Related to the communication and dissemination activities, one of the relevant suggestions by the HLEG is the following:

"The communication and dissemination activities of E-RIHS should be targeted to strengthening the concept of Heritage Science, also at the global scale, and promoting E-RIHS's role in supporting it".

This deliverable will sum the communication and dissemination activities performed in the last three years to identify the strength and weaknesses of the strategy and to improve a new global, impactful strategy. It aims at helping the E-RIHS community implement the HLEG comments.

The deliverable has been drafted by the members of the Communication Office, which is responsible for communication and dissemination activities within E-RIHS PP.

Development and implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy

E-RIHS followed the "smart" principles of communication. By using different monitoring tools, it is possible to identify how much E-RIHS matches the initial objectives.

1.1 Evaluation

Within E-RIHS PP, KPIs were set-up to monitor the quality of the activities. The following KPIs were applied to communication and dissemination activities:

Networking activities

KPI 1. Public events organised by E-RIHS PP

KPI2. Number of participants in the events organised by E-RIHS PP

Dissemination activities

KPI 3. Number of visits to the E-RIHS PP portal

KPI 4. Number of 'share' actions on social networks

KPI 5. Total number of plays of E-RIHS video

KPI 6. Number of quotations of the E-RIHS PP project (in papers)

KPI 7. Number of public events in which E-RIHS PP representatives participate

KPI 8. Number of scientific publications relevant to E-RIHS PP

KPI 9. Number of articles/interviews/reports in the press on E-RIHS PP

KPI 10. Number of newsletters published by E-RIHS PP consortium

KPI11. Number of videos released by the E-RIHS PP consortium

Each of them will be analysed based on the results in E-RIHS to verify the general performance and to identify possible criticalities to solve in a short future.

1.1.1 KPI1 and KPI2. Public events organised by E-RIHS and participants and KPI7. Number of public events in which E-RIHS PP representatives participate

E-RIHS organised nine major international events:

Number event	1
Type of event	International workshop
Title	Towards a European research infrastructure for Heritage Science
Co-organizer/s	-
Date	29.03.2017
Place	Florence, Italy
Number of participants	200

Number event	2
Type of event	International workshop
Title	From cross-disciplinary research to heritage science
Co-organizer/s	IPERION CH, CNR, Opificio delle Pietre Dure
Date	18.10.2018
Place	Florence, Italy
Number of participants	150

Number event	3
Title	Digital HERITAGE 2018 – E-RIHS special session and panel
Co-organizer/s	digital heritage
Date	28.10.2018
Place	San Francisco, US
Number of participants	200

Number event	4
Type of event	International Symposium
Title	Heritage Science: the role of research infrastructures
Co-organizer/s	Federal University of Minas Gerais, Antecipa, Lacicor, Cecor, Bruker
Date	29-30.11.2018
Place	Belo Horizonte, Brazil
Number of participants	70

Number event	5
Type of event	International Symposium
Title	Heritage Science: the role of research infrastructures
Co-organizer/s	IPERION CH, National Laboratory of Sciences for Research and Conservation of Cultural Heritage (LANCIC), CONACYT Network of Applied Sciences for Research and Conservation of Cultural Heritage (CAICPC)
Date	03-04.12.2018
Place	Mexico City, Mexico
Number of participants	50

Number event	6
Type of event	World Meeting on Heritage, Sciences and Technologies – scientific symposium
Title	Frontiers in Heritage Science
Co-organizer/s	French Academy of Sciences, CNRS, IPANEMA and others
Date	14-15.02.2019
Place	Paris, France
Number of participants	1500

Number event	7
Type of event	International colloquium
Title	Leonardo da Vinci: the experience of art
Co-organizer/s	C2RMF, CNRS, IPERION CH
Date	14-15.02.2019
Place	Paris, France
Number of participants	50

Number event	8
Type of event	International colloquium
Title	Instruments at the Services of Heritage Stakeholders
Co-organizer/s	C2RMF, CNRS, IPERION CH, JPI-CH, Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine
Date	23.10.2019
Place	Paris, France
Number of participants	80

Number event	9
Type of event	International workshop
Title	E-RIHS towards the ERIC
Co-organizer/s	E-RIHS
Date	23.09.2020
Place	Virtual, Florence
Number of participants	140

Between 2017 and 2020, many meetings were held to raise awareness of E-RIHS and build new relationships across Europe and beyond. Below there are listed some specific events dedicated to "Communication and Dissemination":

2017, August 27th	
<i>Invited presentation of IPERION CH/E-RIHS at the CIPA 2017 conference in Ottawa</i>	
Type of event	Communication and dissemination
Expected outcomes	Raising awareness about IPERION CH/E-RIHS within the built heritage community

2018, March 15th	
<i>Presentation of IPERION CH/E-RIHS initiatives at Spanish E-RIHS stakeholders at the workshop organised by the Technoheritage Network at IPCE in Madrid.</i>	
Type of event	Communication and dissemination
Expected outcomes	Increase awareness about E-RIHS at the regional level

2018, June 4th	
<i>Presentation of E-RIHS at the SEAHA Conference in London</i>	
Type of event	Communication and dissemination
Expected outcomes	Increase awareness about E-RIHS at the regional level

2018, July 25th	
<i>Sankt Petersburg, presentation of E-RIHS at the conference “Studying Works of Art and Cultural and Historical Heritage: New Technologies and Their Application”</i>	
Type of event	Communication and dissemination
Expected outcomes	Increase awareness about E-RIHS at the global level

2018, September 24th	
<i>Velj Lošinj (Croatia) presentation of E-RIHS at the conference “Transnational Cooperation in Cultural Heritage Science”</i>	
Type of event	Communication and dissemination
Expected outcomes	Increase awareness about E-RIHS at international level

2019, July 2nd	
<i>Santander, presentation of E-RIHS at the summer school “Nuevos retos en la caracterización y conservación de los bienes del patrimonio cultural”</i>	
Type of event	Communication and dissemination
Expected outcomes	Increase awareness about E-RIHS at the regional level

Some of the E-RIHS events have been recorded. Media (photos and videos) and programmes of the events are available at the E-RIHS website (<http://www.e-rihs.eu/international-events/>).

1.1.2 KPI 3. Number of visits to the E-RIHS PP portal

Since the beginning of the project, the E-RIHS website was active, and it was populated with relevant information and news.

Google Analytics returns the following data on the 3-years life of the website:

Number of users	21.000
New users	21.298
Returning visitors	3.473

Pageviews	65.654
Sessions	30.000
Session Duration (average)	2 minutes
Session by country	Italy (20%), UK, United States, The Netherlands, Spain
Most visited pages	Homepage, About us, Partners
Sessions by devices	Desktop (73,3%), Mobile (24.4%), Tablet (2,3%)

Table 1: E-RIHS websites' insights (Google Analytics)

The analysis reveals that the website is the main entry point in E-RIHS life. Returning visitors are 16% of the users, and they mainly visit the home page. They are also curious about the vision, the objectives and the partners. Most likely, their choice depends on the fact that some sections are currently better implemented than others. At the moment, as an example, services are available only in the INFRAIA project IPERION HS (www.iperionhs.eu). The comparison with the analytics of the IPERION CH and HS websites and social media shows that in the INFRAIA projects, people are interested in the pages related to services. Once implemented services in E-RIHS as well, more visitors are expected.

Figure 1: Google Analytics - Behaviour flow in the website

Analysing the data, the identikit of the typical user of the website is represented by the following graphics:

Figure 2: Identikit of the user of the E-RIHS website (Google Analytics, 2020)

1.1.3 KPI 4. Number of ‘share’ actions on social networks

E-RIHS has activated three main social accounts: Facebook, Twitter and Youtube. The social media analysis tracks the online flow of social media communication and measures its impact on the social media target of audiences. This analysis is crucial to draw actionable conclusions for the future strategy and optimise efforts in communicating E-RIHS.

Without measuring and analysing the content of the E-RIHS social media accounts, it is not possible to verify the communication performance and to find a sustainable way of improving it. Social media insights help have a clear overview of the situation and discover critical points to have consistent and successful communication.

	At the beginning (2018)	At the end (September 2020)
Facebook	29 followers	502 followers
Twitter	68 followers Thousands of impressions	601 followers 380 followings Thousands of impressions

Table 2: Comparison between social media insights in 2018 and 2020

Thousands of users were reached in all the social media, and some hundreds engaged. In general, the posts which received more likes and engagement are those with videos and images. For example, the video on Raphael posted on Facebook reached over 3k people, was watched by 800 people, engaged 100 people, and it was retweeted 13 times. The same video posted on Twitter at the same time received 1722 impressions, 180 visualisations, 13 retweets, 12 likes, 7 engagements.

Figure 3: Numbers about the video "E-RIHS meets Raphael" on Facebook (left) and Twitter (right)

Figure 4: Facebook insights shows that media are very engaging

Figure 4 shows how important is designing good visuals for social media for engaging different types of audience.

The analysis of the E-RIHS social media identifies a typical user in their 25-35 years, mostly females, with different provenances. Depending on the social media, data can change slightly, especially with regards to the provenance. This type of data is beneficial to identify the right social media to reach audiences in Europe or across the world.

Figure 5 identifies the users of the E-RIHS Facebook account:

Figure 5: Identikit of E-RIHS Facebook users (Facebook Insights, 2020)

Without commercial analytics tools, today, it is not possible to profiling the users on Twitter. E-RIHS had a general overview of Twitter users only before the Facebook-Cambridge Analytica data scandal (2018). Even if the variance is organic in the social media audience, it is reasonable to suppose that the Twitter audience has not changed very much in two years, mostly because the E-RIHS mission remained the same.

Figure 6: Identikit of E-RIHS Twitter users (Twitter Analytics, 2018)

Recommendations for future – It would be essential to create a "social media" calendar to define the frequency and the topics of the posts to maintain the audience aware of the E-RIHS developments and impact.

Other suggestions:

- rethink about what E-RIHS has to communicate on E-RIHS, enlarge the vision and post news more engaging and consistent
- engage other research infrastructures on common topics and hashtags
- follow and engage new targets of users
- identify key influencers the project wants to attract as followers and engage them in social media campaigns.

1.1.4 KPI 5. The total number of plays of E-RIHS video and KP11. Number of videos released by E-RIHS PP consortium

During the E-RIHS project, videos were produced to raise awareness about E-RIHS and its activities.

Four videos were created to engage social media followers; they were uploaded to Youtube and broadcasted on social media accounts and the E-RIHS website.

1 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=urTiCOG0pM4&t=4s		
	Title	E-RIHS meets Raphael
	Year	2020
	Twitter impressions	1712
	Media views	180
	Total engagements	54
	Likes	12
	Views on Youtube	91

2 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T2Z3j9wml4c&t=5s		
	Title	E-RIHS in Évora
	Year	2020
	Twitter impressions	2365
	Media views	(na)
	Total engagements	54
	Likes	15
	Views on Youtube	94

3 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=orLMTr8t69A&t=6s		
	Title	E-RIHS in London
	Year	2019
	Twitter impressions	2815
	Media views	12
	Total engagements	52
	Likes	9
	Views on Youtube	40

4 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F1vCXaZg3Qw		
	Title	E-RIHS people
	Year	2019
	Twitter impressions	3168
	Media views	430
	Total engagements	86
	Likes	19
	Views on Youtube	10

Other videos are available on the E-RIHS website (<http://www.e-rihs.eu/gallery/>) and tell 360-degrees stories about E-RIHS:

- Participation in international events (international workshops in Florence, Mexico City and Belo Horizonte)
- News in the national nodes (involvement of CENIEH, the launch of the Portuguese node)
- Access experiences (AGLAE, Chiattonne)

Recommendations for the future – Thanks to the analysis of the social media flow, a proposal for the future is to create more (short and long) videos and multimedia materials. As confirmed by the numbers, this type of products has a relevant impact on the social media audience and increase the visibility of E-RIHS.

1.1.5 KPI 6. The number of quotations of the E-RIHS PP project (in papers), KPI 8. The number of scientific publications relevant to E-RIHS PP and KPI 9. Number of articles/interviews/reports in the press on E-RIHS PP

The focus of E-RIHS PP is more political and technical rather than scientific. Still, in the last three years, the E-RIHS community has been committed to consistently raising awareness of E-RIHS's vision and mission. A new sensibility inside the scientific community is growing up, and many of the papers quoting E-RIHS have been published in Open Access.

Due to the lack of properly scientific publications, it is possible to have a general overview of E-RIHS' relevance by analysing the quotations in three different websites:

1. OpenAire
 2. Zenodo
 3. Heritage Science Hub
-
1. Using OpenAire Explore, it is possible to have an idea of the quotations and numbers of the E-RIHS project:
 - 6 publications
 - 2 research data
 - 1 webinar
 2. The E-RIHS community opened a ZENODO account and uploaded the public deliverables. In the Zenodo repository, 18 open access publications and reports are available at the following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/e-rihs/?page=1&size=20>. Keywords are: ERIC; Heritage Science; Access; Assessment; Communication Strategy; Corporate; Cost Benefit Analysis; Data Management; Data Types; Dissemination.
 3. In the Heritage Science Hub (HSH), the semantic tool created inside the E-RIHS project, it is possible to count how many “sources” quote E-RIHS inside a specific flow, named “E-RIHS”, created by the Editorial Board. The flow uses 303 sources and has produced 238 elements that mean quotations.

The screenshot shows the backend interface of the Heritage Science Hub. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Heritage Science Hub' on the left and 'SOURCES', 'FLOWS', and 'CATEGORIES' on the right. Below this is a section titled '< Flows' with a sub-section 'Flow elements' and 'E-RIHS'. The main content area displays five flow elements, each in a white box with a light border. Each element includes a date and time, a title in red, a description, and two buttons: 'UNPUBLISH' and 'EDIT'. The flow elements are:

- September 18, 2020 - 09:34: **SEAHA: RT @ErihsEu: @ErihsEu welcomes all its stakeholders to the final project public workshop,..**
- September 17, 2020 - 10:15: **C2RMF: RT @ErihsEu: @ErihsEu welcomes all its stakeholders to the final project public workshop,..**
- September 17, 2020 - 08:24: **EHRI project: RT @ErihsEu: @ErihsEu welcomes all its stakeholders to the final project public workshop,..**
- August 18, 2020 - 16:11: **Senior Research Fellowship (SSHOC | Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud) | International Institute for Conservation of Historic and Artistic Works**
- August 04, 2020 - 13:48: **IPERION HS Denmark: RT @ErihsEu: Meet E-RIHS scientist: Raffaella Fontana applied the new IR multispectral..**

Table 3: Screenshot of the backend of the Heritage Science Hub (excerpt of quotations)

These tools give an idea of how E-RIHS is perceived and which topics are strategic to the field of heritage science.

Recommendations for the future – E-RIHS continues promoting open science and open access (scientific and not) publications and working on the development of the Heritage Science Hub tool. The idea is to make the HSH a global benchmark in the field of Heritage Science.

1.1.6 KPI 10. Number of newsletters published by E-RIHS PP consortium

This KPI is not measurable because E-RIHS has not published any newsletter. Anyway, in the E-RIHS website, 105 news was published.

Recommendations for the future – It is strongly recommended to create a newsletter about E-RIHS with regular, relevant news (each month, every 2/3 months, every 6 months). Depending on the frequency, it would be possible to keep the E-RIHS community updated and aware of the latest news.

E-RIHS is on the path of becoming an operative infrastructure. In the meanwhile, the IPERION HS integrating activities are providing services to users and keeping the scientific community alive and aware. Excellent scientific results will be published in short under the label IPERION HS and E-RIHS.

1.2 Audience

In the last three years, E-RIHS communication has been addressed to a diversified targeted public:

Type of audience	Engagement
Political stakeholders (Ministries, Scientific Advisory Board, Interim General Assembly, inter-governmental organisations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings with the coordinators or E-RIHS representatives • Meeting with the partners • SAB meetings • IGA meetings • Internal communications via email • Signature of letters of cooperation or intents
E-RIHS community (20 E-RIHS PP partners from 16 different countries, people involved in the E-RIHS national nodes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific international events • News on the website • Social media posts • Videos • Brochure and communication materials • ...
Public at large	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media posts • Videos • Public events

Table 4: Type of audience in E-RIHS (2020)

In a short future, the target of the E-RIHS audience will be changing. For this reason, it will be necessary to revise the communication and dissemination strategy periodically to deliver the right messages to the right audiences.

A more convincing campaign of communication and dissemination will be addressed towards:

- The scientific community at a global level
- The media focused on Heritage Science.

These two targets have been only partially involved in the communication process, and they need more attention. The scientific community at large needs to be aware of the benefits that E-RIHS can offer and have a deeper understanding of E-RIHS goals, activities and perspectives. Sharing results and news with the scientific community helps to use the results better and to ensure follow-up. Media can help E-RIHS enlarge an audience aware of the objectives and the opportunities in setting up this research infrastructure. Media can also help show how the outcomes are relevant to our everyday lives, by creating jobs, introducing new technologies, or improving our lives and heritage better in other ways.

1.3 Internal and external communication

The internal communication has ensured an effective exchange and share of information between the partners. Emails were sent by a unique email address (co@e-rihs.eu) to simplify the bidirectional communication (from E-RIHS; towards E-RIHS). Depending on the subject, incoming emails were responded by the person in charge of that specific subject in the Central Management Office. Project meetings have been scheduled periodically, and their dates communicated well in advance to partners. An Eventbrite registration form has been created and adapted to help a rational and customised organisation of the meetings by the hosting partners.

The essential documentation has been uploaded to D4science (<https://www.d4science.org/>) in the E-RIHS VRE and shared with all the partners.

Special folders were created to answer specific needs.

Key messages are essential to the communication and dissemination strategy, but they need to be revised continuously. E-RIHS is entering a new phase of its paths towards the ERIC. While the key intents remain the same (raise awareness, inform, educate, engage), the key messages need an update to stay consistent with the E-RIHS strategy.

1.3.1 Communication at time of emergency as a challenge

The Covid-19 emergency brought about an unusual situation in the communication flow. After the last meeting in Évora, Portugal, the consortium was not able to meet in person anymore. The final event was scheduled in Florence, Italy, but the emergency obliged to reschedule it online. Despite all, all the activities and meetings continued online by using the ZOOM platform.

The status of emergency obliged to a more in-depth discussion inside E-RIHS on the digital issues, also involving communication. First of all, the crisis made clear the impact of science on people's behaviour and the urgency for good quality science communication. E-RIHS needs to have this in mind to better design its future communication strategy.

Secondly, the crisis makes the DIGILAB implementation urgent. Since the beginning of the project, E-RIHS has been working on the new digital platform. Unfortunately, the implementation plan has required more time and efforts than expected. For this reason, E-RIHS is still elaborating an implementation plan. Once ready, DIGILAB will contribute to setting up new, more robust strategies also in E-RIHS communication.

Conclusions

The **Report on the implementation and evaluation of communication** demonstrates how important is the monitoring of the activities over time. Some way, the objectives set up at the beginning of the E-RIHS PP project are grown up. New communities such as paleoanthropologists, archaeologists and built environment researchers joined the E-RIHS community and enlarged the vision. New opportunities across Europe and beyond have put the basis of fruitful international cooperation. The Covid-19 emergency has had a substantial impact on the dynamic activities carried out since the beginning of January 2020. It compels to a more in-depth reflection and a new vision for the future of the research infrastructures, possibly also new approaches.

In the last three years, the E-RIHS PP project has carried out the communication and dissemination activities as described in the "Communication and Dissemination Plan" (D10.1) and set up all the tools necessary to manage internal and external communication. The "Visual Guidelines" and the "Toolkit for E-RIHS events" helped the partners to make the communication in the national nodes consistent and to organise events under the "E-RIHS" label.

In March 2020, the Communication Office verified the E-RIHS strategy by using the criteria set up in the "Communication toolkit for European Research Infrastructures", released by the RI-VIS project in March 2020. The E-RIHS strategy is perfectly in agreement with the suggested one by RI-VIS.

E-RIHS has gone further. In December 2018, the Communication Office delivered the report D10.2, "Heritage Hub online in project website" (Dec. 2018). The Report describes an innovative and semantic web tool acting as a hub of information in the field of Heritage Science. It was designed as a cloud service for sharing specific and multiform interests and information in an effective way. In the last two years, the Communication Office worked hard to upgrade this tool. At the moment, the tool is not visible on the public frontend of the E-RIHS website. The idea is to improve its performance further and release the new version only when the tool will be implemented and consolidated. It is a question of brand reputation. The goal is ambitious: the tool is unique in the field of Heritage Science and better design means to propose it truly as a benchmark.

